

MANIFESTATION AND IMPORTANCE OF EMOTIONAL RESILIENCE IN A PERSON'S STRESS

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Abstract: In this article, the manifestation of emotional resilience of a person in a stressful situation, its study by foreign scientists is analyzed. It is stated that emotional resilience as a personality trait consists of several components.

Key words: Emotional resilience, emotional experiences, stress resilience, emotion, emotion, locus of control.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется проявление эмоциональной устойчивости человека в стрессовой ситуации, ее изучение зарубежными учеными. Утверждается, что эмоциональная устойчивость как свойство личности состоит из нескольких компонентов.

Ключевые слова: Эмоциональная устойчивость, эмоциональные переживания, стрессоустойчивость, эмоция, эмоция, локус контроля.

Global experts emphasize that stress has become the "disease of the century". After all, the stress of a person has a serious negative impact not only on his activities, but also on his mental and physical health. According to WHO, the cause of 65% of existing diseases is related to stress. According to the records of this organization, at the WHO assembly held in Geneva, stress was included in the International Classification of Diseases under number 11. According to the American Psychological Association, "stress ... is a major threat to human health, and if people do not learn healthy ways to manage current stressors, it can seriously affect their health." league is emphasized. Therefore, it is important to study that the stress of a person has a serious negative impact not only on his activities, but also on his mental and physical health. Globally, stress and resilience to stress is one of the urgent problems in the field of psychology, and in researches, it is necessary to determine the psychophysiological factors that cause it, to influence the motivational, emotional-volitional sphere of people prone to stress, to strengthen their mental health, as a result of the negative complications of stress observed among people. wide-ranging scientific researches are being carried out on issues such as the decrease in the quality of work, the issue of competitive personnel training, social-psychological prevention of stress-prone individuals, and ensuring the effectiveness of effective psychocorrective methods.

Despite the large amount of work done on this problem, the true nature of the concept of stress resistance, the role of the psyche in its maintenance, and the specific aspects of its manifestation in various activities are still problems. there is. However, these questions are reflected in the concept of "emotional resilience", which is somewhat synonymous with the concept of stress resilience that we are studying.

A number of authors associate emotional resilience with temperamental characteristics that affect not the content of emotional experiences and sorrows, but their speed and strength in a certain sense.

Other researchers believe that emotional resilience is the ability to control emotions that arise in the process of performing activities, connecting them with willpower characteristics of a person. The studies of M.I.Dyachenko and K.Izard believe that emotional resilience is determined by the dynamic (speed, flexibility, lability) and content (type of emotions and feelings, their level) characteristics of the emotional process in a certain sense. An important factor of emotional resilience is determined by the content and level of emotions and feelings in extreme situations. P. B. Zilberman comes to the conclusion that the term "emotional resilience" means the integrative features of a person, which are related to the emotional, volitional, intellectual and motivational components of mental activity and ensure the achievement of the desired goal even in difficult emotional situations. In this regard, many authors came to the opinion that emotional resilience is a characteristic of the psyche, manifested in the ability of a person to maintain emotional stability in difficult situations and successfully perform the necessary activities. M. I. D'yachenko and V. A. Ponamarenko further improve the opinions expressed in relation to this situation and consider that it is very important to clarify the place and role of the personal emotional component in the nature of the psyche. Otherwise, emotional resilience can be confused with will and mental resilience, which are integral characteristics of a person. In other words, the implementation of necessary actions in difficult situations depends not only on emotional endurance, but also on other characteristics and experiences of a person. According to the authors, the following are emotional determinants of stress resistance: emotional assessment of the situation, emotional observation of the progress of the activity and its results, emotions and feelings experienced in this situation, emotional experience of the person (emotional assumptions, images, previous experiences). Research by the above authors shows that emotional resilience as a personality trait consists of the following components:

- a) motivational
- b) emotional
- c) volitional (manifested in the ability to consciously control the activity and bring the situation to an orderly appearance)
- g) intellectual - the ability to determine and evaluate the requirements of the situation, to foresee its change, and to make decisions about means of activity.

A person's ability to show emotional resilience in extreme situations indicates that the psyche has risen to a new level of activity. The restoration of such motivational, managerial and implementing functions serves not only to maintain professional activity, but also to increase its efficiency.

A number of researchers have tried to establish a universal principle for dividing people into those who are resistant and those who are resistant to stress. Thus, G. Sele connects the active and passive behavior of people in a state of stress with their individual hormonal differences. According to V.A. Faivyshevskiy, different people experience positive or negative emotions in a certain stressful situation, it is related to the degree of arousal of their positive or negative motivations. J. Rotter notes that people are affected differently in stress depending on whether they have an external (external) or internal (internal) locus-controlled character.

According to the conclusion of the analysis of the literature conducted by A.M. Bokovikov, the level of stress resistance is not related to the indicators of intro-extroversion, but has an inverse correlation with the level of neuroticism. R. Lazarus people with a high level of neuroticism have a very weak ability to evaluate their personal resources: they are often inadequately evaluated, and naturally they cannot correctly evaluate stressful situations. On the contrary, emotionally resilient individuals evaluate stressful situations as a warning, a need, and an effort to actively overcome them. Current knowledge about "internal" and "external" stress resistance, including the inability to control the stressful situation, is contradictory and does not allow to confirm that it is a factor that ensures the individual's stress resistance. Stress resistance is based on social introversion and extraversion. There have been many attempts to analyze it. Among them, the stress resistance analysis system proposed by H.J. Eysenck based on the indicators of neuroticism, introversion and extroversion attracted wide public opinion.

The limitations of the existing analysis systems are related to the multi-component nature of stress resistance and the methodological difficulties of being able to evaluate them uniformly, on the one hand, and the diversity of personal characteristics prevents them from being truthfully evaluated.

Nowadays, a universal law is followed that connects the intensity of stress with the activity of the nervous system and the efficiency of the activity. The researches of R. Erkes and J. Dodson showed that the increase in the level of activity of the nervous system up to a certain critical point ensures the efficiency of the activity. A further increase in the activity of the nervous system in conditions of continuous stress lowers the indicator of activity results. D. E. Broadbent's research proved that stressful effects increase the efficiency of simpler activities and at the same time lead to early breakdown of more difficult activities.

Based on the above considerations about stress, it is necessary to maintain the physical and psychological condition of a person in stressful situations, and at the same time to ensure the quality of professional activity required of him. In a word, resistance to stress is measured by the value of resistance of individual processes of the psyche. Of course, the level of endurance of professionally important mental characteristics ensures the individual's resistance to stress, but cannot determine it.

Based on this, the characteristics of the manifestation and management of human stress resistance are:

- a) motivation and goal-oriented behavior;
- b) functional resources and their level of activation;
- c) personal characteristics and cognitive abilities;
- g) emotional-volitional reactivity;
- d) is explained by professional training and ability to work.

The characteristic of stress resistance is the resilience of the organism and psyche to the effects of stress factors, their resistance and tolerance to extreme effects, regardless of the level of its management and manifestation, and the ability of a person in concrete extreme situations. functional flexibility (adaptation) in life and work, and finally compensation of extreme functional disorders that occur in stressful situations.

So, the fact that a stressful situation leaves severe or mild complications in a person is related to the formation of emotional resilience in each person from the psychological and physiological side.

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